

DELAMINATION MODEL FOR CROSS-PLY LAMINATES SUBJECT TO BIAXIAL LOADING AND THERMAL STRESSES

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SUMMARY

This paper addresses the issue of using energy balance methods and crack closure concepts to predict the steady growth of delaminations associated with ply cracks during the progressive loading of cross-ply laminates subject to a combination of in-plane biaxial and thermal residual stresses.

Keywords: Delamination, energy release rate, GRP, CFRP, boundary element method.

INTRODUCTION

Progressive ply crack formation in cross-ply laminates is often accompanied at the later stages of loading by the appearance of delaminations that are understood to have initiated from ply cracks. It is of interest, therefore, to be able to predict the degree of loading required to enable delaminations, that have already initiated at ply cracks, to grow along the interfaces between the 0° and 90° plies and meet delaminations growing in the opposite direction. This problem has been investigated recently using a boundary element method (BEM) [1], which provides very accurate energy release rates for delaminations, and accounts for mechanical contacts between crack faces. When neighbouring ply cracks are wide apart and the delamination length is large enough, there exists a 'steady state' region where delamination energy release rates are independent of delamination length when applied loads and temperature are held fixed during delamination growth. This 'steady state' value is of importance when assessing the threat of significant laminate damage in the form of inter-ply delaminations.

O'Brien [2] developed, for cross-ply laminates, an analytical model determining the value of the applied uniaxial stress for 'steady state' delamination. The model assumes that the transverse stresses in both 0° and 90° plies are zero everywhere. This situation can never occur in practice as bonded 0° and 90° plies always exhibit the same transverse strain and this leads to non-zero transverse ply stresses away from laminate edges, even when the net transverse load is zero. The objective of this paper is to show how the O'Brien model can be extended by considering how to deal with biaxial in-

plane loading combined with thermal residual stresses characterized by the difference between the laminate temperature and its stress-free temperature.

GEOMETRY

Consider a region of a $[0_m/90_n]_s$ laminate of width $2W$ having an array of equally spaced ply cracks in the 90° ply having separation $2L$. The ply thicknesses of the 0° and 90° plies are denoted respectively by $h^{(0)}$ and $h^{(90)}$, so that the total thickness $2h = 2(h^{(0)} + h^{(90)})$. Delaminations of equal length c are growing in the interfaces between the 90° ply and the 0° plies, having been initiated at the tips of the ply cracks as shown in Fig.1. In each one of the interfaces the total delaminated length in the region between two neighbouring ply cracks is thus $2c$. The effective axial and in-plane stresses are σ and σ_T respectively, and the through-thickness stress is zero.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of damaged laminate illustrating the geometry and loading.

UNDAMAGED LAMINATE

Consider first of all the undamaged laminate having effective in-plane stress-strain relations given by

$$\epsilon^0 = \frac{\sigma}{E_A^0} - \frac{\nu_A^0}{E_A^0} \sigma_T + \alpha_A^0 \Delta T, \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_T^0 = -\frac{\nu_A^0}{E_A^0} \sigma + \frac{\sigma_T}{E_T^0} + \alpha_T^0 \Delta T, \quad (2)$$

where ϵ^0 and ϵ_T^0 are respectively the axial and transverse strains for an *undamaged* laminate subject to effective in-plane axial and transverse applied stresses σ and σ_T respectively, and to thermal stresses characterized by the difference ΔT between the temperature of the laminate and its stress-free temperature. For an undamaged laminate,

the axial and transverse Young's moduli are denoted by E_A^0 and E_T^0 respectively, the major axial Poisson's ratio is denoted by ν_A^0 , and the axial and transverse thermal expansion coefficients are denoted by α_A^0 and α_T^0 respectively.

When the transverse strain ϵ_T^0 is specified, it follows from (2) that the corresponding effective transverse stress is given by

$$\sigma_T = \sigma_T^0 = \nu_A^0 \frac{E_T^0}{E_A^0} \sigma + E_T^0 \epsilon_T^0 - E_T^0 \alpha_T^0 \Delta T. \quad (3)$$

Substitution in (1) then leads to the following value for the axial strain

$$\epsilon^0 = \frac{\sigma}{\hat{E}_A^0} - \nu_A^0 \frac{E_T^0}{E_A^0} \epsilon_T^0 + \hat{\alpha}_A^0 \Delta T, \quad (4)$$

where the reduced axial Young's modulus \hat{E}_A^0 and axial thermal expansion coefficient $\hat{\alpha}_A^0$ are defined by

$$\hat{E}_A^0 = \frac{E_A^0}{1 - (\nu_A^0)^2 E_T^0 / E_A^0}, \quad \hat{\alpha}_A^0 = \alpha_A^0 + \nu_A^0 \frac{E_T^0}{E_A^0} \alpha_T^0. \quad (5)$$

These values correspond to the plane strain axial modulus and expansion coefficient.

EFFECTIVE STRESSES AND STRAINS

When considering damage formation in laminates, it is vital to introduce the concepts of effective stresses and strains. The damaged laminate, having ply cracks and delaminations, is assumed to be subject to imposed uniform axial displacements $\pm\delta$ on $y = \pm L$, which can vary, leading to an effective axial strain $\epsilon = \delta/L$. For generalized plane strain conditions, the transverse strain has the value ϵ_T everywhere in the *damaged* laminate, and the transverse displacements on $z = \pm W$ have the values $\pm W \epsilon_T$. Because of the presence of damage, the traction distributions on $y = \pm L$ and on $z = \pm W$ will be non-uniform and it is necessary to introduce effective axial and transverse stresses σ and σ_T defined respectively by

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{4Wh} \int_{-W}^W \int_{-h}^h \sigma_{yy}(x, L, z) dx dz, \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_T = \frac{1}{4Lh} \int_{-L}^L \int_{-h}^h \sigma_{zz}(x, y, W) dx dy. \quad (7)$$

Effective stress-strain relations for the damaged laminate are then given by

$$\epsilon = \frac{\sigma}{E_A} - \frac{\nu_A}{E_A} \sigma_T + \alpha_A \Delta T, \quad (8)$$

$$\epsilon_T = -\frac{\nu_A}{E_A} \sigma + \frac{\sigma_T}{E_T} + \alpha_T \Delta T, \quad (9)$$

where, for a *damaged* laminate, E_A and E_T are the effective axial and transverse Young's moduli, ν_A is the axial Poisson's ratio, α_A and α_T are the axial and transverse thermal expansion coefficients, and where there is an assumed dependence of the

thermo-elastic constants on the uniform ply crack density and the length c of these delaminations. The definitions of the effective elastic constants in (8) and (9) are based on the assumption that the in-plane transverse strain is everywhere uniform.

Consider now situations where the axial stress σ and the transverse strain ε_T are prescribed and remain fixed as the delaminations grow. The stress-strain relations (8) and (9) then imply that both the axial strain ε and the effective transverse stress σ_T will depend on the ply crack density and the length c of the delaminations. In principle, it is possible to allow the transverse strain ε_T to vary so that the effective transverse stress σ_T remains fixed at the prescribed value σ_T^0 as damage develops, although it is then more difficult to obtain numerical solutions. It should be noted that, if the transverse strain $\varepsilon_T = 0$ for any values of the axial stress and temperature, then plane strain conditions are modelled.

CRACK CLOSURE

Before considering the energetics of delamination growth in more detail, consider the closure of both ply cracks and delaminations. First of all, consider the special case when the loading is uniaxial in the *axial* direction (so that $\sigma = \sigma_c$, $\sigma_T = \sigma_T^0 = 0$) and the axial load is such that the ply cracks are *just* closed. For cases where crack contacts are frictionless it is expected, and has been confirmed to within numerical error using an accurate BEM, that the delaminations also will *just* close. The BEM code applied in the present work is in-house software that solves the Somigliana displacement identity by the standard collocation approach using linear continuous elements in the way described by París and Cañas [3]; boundary conditions along the interfaces between the plies are applied using the weak approach developed by Blázquez et al [4]; and the effects of transverse strain are included using the procedure described by Blázquez et al [5].

Another way of understanding such closure is to consider the uniaxial axial loading of an undamaged laminate where the axial stress in the 90° ply is everywhere zero and where the tractions on the ply interfaces are also everywhere zero. In this state, ply cracks and delaminations can be introduced anywhere the laminate without the stress and displacement fields being perturbed. Thus, at the point of closure, the axial stress, and the axial and in-plane transverse strains, have the same values in both damaged and undamaged laminates so that, from (1), (2), (8) and (9)

$$\varepsilon^c = \frac{\sigma^c}{E_A} + \alpha_A \Delta T, \quad \varepsilon_T^c = -\frac{\nu_A}{E_A} \sigma^c + \alpha_T \Delta T, \quad (10)$$

$$\varepsilon^c = \frac{\sigma^c}{E_A^0} + \alpha_A^0 \Delta T, \quad \varepsilon_T^c = -\frac{\nu_A^0}{E_A^0} \sigma^c + \alpha_T^0 \Delta T, \quad (11)$$

where σ_c is the closure stress for uniaxial loading in the axial direction and where ε^c and ε_T^c are respectively the corresponding axial and transverse closure strains. Elimination of the closure strains leads to the relations

$$\left(\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right) \sigma^c = - (\alpha_A - \alpha_A^0) \Delta T, \quad (12)$$

$$\left(\frac{v_A^0}{E_A^0} - \frac{v_A}{E_A} \right) \sigma^c = - (\alpha_T - \alpha_T^0) \Delta T. \quad (13)$$

Consider another special case where the loading is uniaxial in the in-plane *transverse* direction and the transverse load σ_T^c is such that the ply cracks are again just closed. For cases where crack contacts are frictionless, it is again expected that the delaminations also will just close, for the same reasons used when considering uniaxial axial loading. BEM results have again confirmed this type of closure to within numerical error. It then follows that, at the point of closure, the transverse stress and both the axial and in-plane transverse strains will have the same value in both damaged and undamaged laminates so that, from (1), (2), (8) and (9),

$$\left(\frac{v_A^0}{E_A^0} - \frac{v_A}{E_A} \right) \sigma_T^c = - (\alpha_A - \alpha_A^0) \Delta T, \quad (14)$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{E_T} - \frac{1}{E_T^0} \right) \sigma_T^c = - (\alpha_T - \alpha_T^0) \Delta T. \quad (15)$$

It has been shown [6] that the crack closure stresses σ^c and σ_T^c are given by

$$\sigma^c = - \frac{\alpha_A - \alpha_A^0}{\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0}} \Delta T = - \frac{\alpha_T - \alpha_T^0}{\frac{v_A^0}{E_A^0} - \frac{v_A}{E_A}} \Delta T = -k_1 \Delta T, \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_T^c = - \frac{\alpha_A - \alpha_A^0}{\frac{v_A^0}{E_A^0} - \frac{v_A}{E_A}} \Delta T = - \frac{\alpha_T - \alpha_T^0}{\frac{1}{E_T} - \frac{1}{E_T^0}} \Delta T = -k_2 \Delta T, \quad (17)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are *undamaged* laminate constants defined by

$$k_1 = \frac{h^{(0)} E_A}{h} \frac{h^{(0)} E_T + h^{(90)} E_A - h v_A E_T}{h^{(0)} E_T + h^{(90)} E_A - h v_A^2 E_T} (\alpha_A - \alpha_T), \quad (18)$$

$$k_2 = \left[h^{(0)} E_T + h^{(90)} E_A - h v_A E_T \right] \frac{E_A (\alpha_A - \alpha_T)}{h v_A (E_A - E_T)}, \quad (19)$$

where the thermo-elastic constants of the 0° ply are shown in *italics*. It follows from (16) and (17) that the following inter-relationships must be satisfied

$$\frac{\frac{v_A^0}{E_A^0} - \frac{v_A}{E_A}}{\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0}} = \frac{\frac{1}{E_T} - \frac{1}{E_T^0}}{\frac{v_A^0}{E_A^0} - \frac{v_A}{E_A}} = \frac{\alpha_T - \alpha_T^0}{\alpha_A - \alpha_A^0} = \frac{k_1}{k_2} = k, \quad (20)$$

where k is an *undamaged* laminate constant independent of thermal expansion coefficients, derived from (18) and (19), given by

$$k = \frac{v_A h^{(0)} (E_A - E_T)}{h^{(0)} E_T + h^{(90)} E_A - h v_A^2 E_T}. \quad (21)$$

It then follows from (16) and (17) that

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{v_A^0}{E_A^0} - \frac{v_A}{E_A} &= k \left(\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right), & \frac{1}{E_T} - \frac{1}{E_T^0} &= k^2 \left(\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right), \\ \alpha_A - \alpha_A^0 &= k_1 \left(\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right), & \alpha_T - \alpha_T^0 &= k k_1 \left(\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right).\end{aligned}\quad (22)$$

GIBBS FREE ENERGY

Since $\varepsilon = -\partial G / \partial \sigma$ and $\varepsilon_T = -\partial G / \partial \sigma_T$, and on using (8) and (9), it follows that the Gibbs free energy averaged per unit volume G for a cracked cross-ply laminate must have the form

$$G = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2E_A} - \frac{\sigma_T^2}{2E_T} + \frac{v_A}{E_A} \sigma \sigma_T - \sigma \alpha_A \Delta T - \sigma_T \alpha_T \Delta T + \bar{G}, \quad (23)$$

where the term \bar{G} represents the Gibbs free energy per unit volume when the *damaged* laminate is unloaded. The value of \bar{G} is independent of the loading parameters σ , σ_T but it will depend on the damage if thermal residual stresses are present. To avoid the problem of estimating \bar{G} , it is useful to consider the crack closure state where it is expected that all ply cracks and delaminations will be *just* closed, assuming frictionless contact of crack faces, as discussed above. For such closure conditions, the stress and deformation distribution in the laminate is identical to that in the corresponding undamaged laminate subject to the same applied stresses and temperature. Consider the crack closure situation that arises when the laminate is uniaxially loaded in the axial direction so that $\sigma = \sigma^c$, $\sigma_T = 0$. It follows from (23) that the Gibbs free energy G_c per unit volume for such closure conditions is given by

$$G_c = -\sigma^c \left(\frac{\sigma^c}{2E_A} + \alpha_A \Delta T \right) + \bar{G}, \quad (24)$$

leading to the following expression for \bar{G}

$$\bar{G} = \sigma^c \left(\frac{\sigma^c}{2E_A} + \alpha_A \Delta T \right) + G_c. \quad (25)$$

The value of G_c is easily calculated as its value does not depend on the damage present, although its value is not actually needed. For general loading conditions, the Gibbs free energy per unit volume is then given by

$$G = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2E_A} - \frac{\sigma_T^2}{2E_T} + \frac{v_A}{E_A} \sigma \sigma_T - \sigma \alpha_A \Delta T - \sigma_T \alpha_T \Delta T + \sigma^c \left[\frac{\sigma^c}{2E_A} + \alpha_A \Delta T \right] + G_c. \quad (26)$$

The corresponding value for the Gibbs free energy per unit volume when the laminate is undamaged is given by

$$G_0 = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2E_A^0} - \frac{\sigma_T^2}{2E_T^0} + \frac{v_A^0}{E_A^0} \sigma \sigma_T - \sigma \alpha_A^0 \Delta T - \sigma_T \alpha_T^0 \Delta T + \sigma^c \left[\frac{\sigma^c}{2E_A^0} + \alpha_A^0 \Delta T \right] + G_c. \quad (27)$$

A subtraction eliminates G_c leading to

$$\begin{aligned}
G - G_0 = & -\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right) - \frac{\sigma_T^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{E_T} - \frac{1}{E_T^0} \right) + \left(\frac{v_A}{E_A} - \frac{v_A^0}{E_A^0} \right) \sigma \sigma_T \\
& - \sigma (\alpha_A - \alpha_A^0) \Delta T - \sigma_T (\alpha_T - \alpha_T^0) \Delta T + \sigma^c \left[\frac{\sigma^c}{2} \left(\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right) + (\alpha_A - \alpha_A^0) \Delta T \right]. \quad (28)
\end{aligned}$$

On using (22), it then follows that the Gibbs free energy per unit volume of damaged laminate may be written in the very simple form

$$G = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right) \left[\sigma + k \sigma_T - \sigma^c \right]^2 + G_0, \quad \text{where} \quad \sigma^c = -k_1 \Delta T. \quad (29)$$

ENERGY RELEASE RATE

The next step is to make use of the result (29) to calculate the total energy release rate associated with the growth of the delaminations in the interfaces between the 0° and 90° plies for conditions of generalized plane strain where the effective axial stress σ , the transverse stress σ_T and temperature difference ΔT are prescribed. The damage in the laminate is characterised by the uniform ply crack density $1/(2L)$ and the length c of the four delaminations associated with each ply crack. The effective axial modulus E_A will depend on both ρ and c , but the quantities E_A^0 , k , k_1 and G_0 will all be independent of these damage parameters. By considering a representative region ($2L \times 2W \times 2h$) containing four delamination crack tips, it has been shown [6] that the energy balance equation is,

$$\frac{2\gamma}{hL} \delta c + \delta G = -\varepsilon \delta \sigma - \varepsilon_T \delta \sigma_T, \quad (30)$$

where 2γ is the effective fracture energy for delamination. On taking the limit $\delta c \rightarrow 0$, keeping σ and σ_T fixed, the energy-based fracture criterion reduces to the following form

$$\frac{2\gamma}{hL} + \frac{\partial G}{\partial c} = 0. \quad (31)$$

The fixed value of σ_T during delamination growth implies that the uniform transverse strain ε_T will depend on the delamination length. It then follows, on using (29), that the energy release rate, as a result of delamination growth, may be written

$$ERR = 2\gamma = -Lh \frac{\partial G}{\partial c} = \frac{1}{2} Lh \left[\sigma + k \sigma_T - \sigma^c \right]^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial c} \left(\frac{1}{E_A} \right), \quad (32)$$

which assumes that the applied stresses σ , σ_T , the temperature difference ΔT , and the ply crack density all remain fixed during delamination growth. The relation (32) provides an alternative method of estimating energy release rates for delamination that can be compared with results obtained numerically when using the virtual crack extension method (see [7] for an example of an application of this method to a GRP laminate).

SELF-SIMILAR DELAMINATION GROWTH

Consider now the special case where the uniform ply crack density is low so that neighbouring ply cracks are widely separated, and where the delamination crack tips are well away from the ply cracks but not interacting with other delaminations that are present between neighbouring ply cracks. For this case the stress and deformation in regions well away from the delamination tips will not be affected by delamination growth because delamination growth is self-similar or 'steady state'. For generalized plane strain and uniaxial loading conditions it is then possible to estimate the change of effective modulus of the laminate arising from delamination growth.

A region of laminate is first considered that occupies the region $0 < y < L - c - a$, where $a > 0$ is fixed when the delamination length c increases. In this region having length $L - c - a$, the laminate is undamaged and its effective axial modulus is E_A^0 , the effective uniaxial axial stress is denoted by σ and the corresponding transverse strain is given by $\epsilon_T = -(\nu_A^0 / E_A^0)\sigma + \alpha_T^0 \Delta T$. Consider the region $L - c + a < y < L$ of length $c - a$ in which the interfaces are entirely debonded due to the presence of the delamination cracks. For the constrained condition under discussion, the transverse strain in both the 0° and 90° plies must have the same value ϵ_T in this region. It is clear that the axial stress in each 0° is $h\sigma/h^{(0)}$. It can be shown that the effective axial modulus \bar{E}_A for this region is then given by

$$\frac{1}{\bar{E}_A} = \frac{1}{E_A} \left[\left(1 - \nu_A^2 \frac{E_T}{E_A} \right) \frac{h}{h^{(0)}} + \nu_A E_T \frac{\nu_A^0}{E_A^0} \right], \quad (33)$$

where the elastic constants for the 0° plies are shown in *italics*. In the remaining region occupying the region $L - c - a < y < L - c + a$ having length $2a$ that moves with the delamination tip during growth, the stress and deformation distributions are very complex but are such that the transverse strain has the uniform value ϵ_T just defined. The stress and strain distributions do not vary as the delaminations increase their length, i.e. delamination growth is self-similar, with the result that the average transverse stress acting over this region is independent of the delamination length c . The effective modulus of this region is denoted by E_0 and will be independent of the delamination length c . It then follows that the effective modulus E_A of the three regions together may be obtained using the following relation based on the consideration of the axial displacements

$$\frac{L}{E_A} = \frac{L - c - a}{E_A^0} + \frac{c - a}{\bar{E}_A} + \frac{2a}{E_0}. \quad (34)$$

As a is independent of c , it then follows that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial c} \left(\frac{1}{E_A} \right) = \frac{1}{L} \left(\frac{1}{\bar{E}_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right). \quad (35)$$

Substitution in (32), valid for biaxial loading conditions, then leads to the following expression for the energy release rate for delamination under self-similar growth conditions

$$\text{ERR} = \frac{1}{2}h \left[\sigma + k \sigma_T - \sigma^c \right]^2 \left(\frac{1}{\bar{E}_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right). \quad (36)$$

It is useful to compare this result with that obtained using O'Brien's model [2] for steady state delamination in a $[0_m/90_n]_s$ cross-ply laminate, which applies only for uniaxial stress states and neglects thermal residual stresses, namely

$$\text{ERR} = \frac{1}{2}h \sigma^2 \left(\frac{h}{h^{(0)}E_A} - \frac{1}{E_A^0} \right). \quad (37)$$

This result differs from (36), which shows how O'Brien's result may corrected to account for non-zero transverse ply stresses when the transverse load is zero, and generalized to deal with non-zero effective transverse laminate stresses and thermal stresses. It should be noted that, if the Poisson's ratios are set to zero in (33), then $\bar{E}_A = E_A h^{(0)} / h$ and the result (36) then agrees with that of O'Brien for conditions of uniaxial loading in the absence of thermal residual stresses, as to be expected.

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

For the investigation a simple $[0/90]_s$ laminate, where the ply thickness is 0.25 mm, has been selected that has the following transverse isotropic properties typical of a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy material:

$$\begin{array}{llll} E_A = 141.3 \text{ GPa} & E_T = E_t = 9.58 \text{ GPa} & \nu_A = \nu_a = 0.3 & \nu_T = 0.32 \\ \mu_A = \mu_a = 5.0 \text{ GPa} & \mu_T = 3.629 \text{ GPa} & \alpha_A = -1 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C} & \alpha_T = 2.6 \times 10^{-5} / ^\circ\text{C}. \end{array}$$

Both the analytical and boundary element models require a value for the temperature difference $\Delta T = T - T_0$ where T is the uniform applied temperature and T_0 is the stress-free temperature for the laminate at which all stress and strain components have zero values. When $\Delta T \neq 0$ thermal residual stresses are present that will affect the energy release rate for delamination. The laminate is assumed either to be free of thermal stresses (i.e. $\Delta T = 0$) or simulated at a temperature T that is 100°C lower than the stress-free temperature of the laminate so that $\Delta T = -100^\circ\text{C}$.

When the ply crack separation $2L = 10$ mm and the delamination length $c = 2.5$ mm, accurate BEM calculations have been undertaken for the case when the effective axial strain applied to the damaged laminate is 1%, and the transverse strain is fixed everywhere so that $\epsilon_T = -(\nu_A^0 / E_A^0) \sigma + \alpha_T^0 \Delta T$ which is the value arising in an undamaged laminate subjected to an axial strain of 1% and zero effective in-plane transverse stress. The BEM calculations lead to an effective axial stress σ and effective transverse stress σ_T associated with an imposed transverse strain ϵ_T such that:

$$\begin{array}{l} \sigma = 0.731 \text{ GPa}, \sigma_T = -0.00796 \text{ GPa}, \epsilon_T = -0.000381 \text{ when } \Delta T = 0^\circ\text{C}, \\ \sigma = 0.733 \text{ GPa}, \sigma_T = -0.0194 \text{ GPa}, \epsilon_T = -0.0005 \text{ when } \Delta T = -100^\circ\text{C}. \end{array}$$

Table 1 shows the BEM results estimated using the virtual crack extension technique. It is seen that thermal residual stresses lead to a very large increase in the energy release rate for delamination. An attempt is now made to obtain approximate values for the energy release rates for delamination based on the analysis described above.

For conditions of self-similar delamination, use can be made of the result (36). The results shown in Table 1 under the heading ‘steady state’ have used the axial and transverse applied stresses obtained using the BEM, and the expression (33) for \bar{E}_A .

Table 1: Energy release rates (J/m^2) for delamination in typical damaged CFRP.

ΔT °C	BEM J/m^2	Steady state J/m^2	O’Brien [2] J/m^2
0	114.7	117.6	128.4
-100	181.0	184.6	-

It is seen from Table 1 that the steady state results are very slightly higher than those obtained using the BEM. The reason for this slight discrepancy is thought to be associated with the use of a value for the ply crack separation $2L = 10$ mm that is not large enough for precise steady state conditions to prevail (i.e. there is a slight interaction between the ply cracks and the delaminations). Also shown in Table 1 are values for the energy release rate when using O’Brien’s formula (37) for the case $\Delta T = 0$. These preliminary results show that, when thermal residual stresses are absent, O’Brien’s result over-estimates the energy release rate for interfacial delamination, as Poisson contraction effects have been ignored.

CONCLUSION

The new analytical results for the prediction of the steady state energy release rate for delamination are in good agreement with, and exceed, results obtained using the BEM so that the model is expected to be slightly conservative.

REFERENCES

1. A. Blázquez, V. Mantič, F. Paris and L. N. McCartney, ‘Stress state characterization of delamination cracks in [0/90] symmetric laminates by BEM’, *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, **45**, 1632-62, 2008.
2. T. K. O’Brien, ‘Analysis of local delaminations and their influence on composite laminate behaviour’, *ASTM STP 876*, 282-297, 1985.
3. F. Paris and J. Cañas, *Boundary Element Method. Fundamentals and Applications*, Oxford University Press, 1997.
4. A. Blázquez, F. Paris and V. Mantič, ‘BEM solution of two-dimensional contact problems by weak application of contact conditions with non-conforming discretizations’, *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, **35**, 3259-3278, 1998.
5. A. Blázquez, V. Mantič and F. Paris, ‘Application of BEM to generalized plane problems for anisotropic elastic materials in presence of contact’, *Engng. Anal. Boundary Elements*, **30**, 489-502, 2006.
6. L. N. McCartney and A. Blázquez, to be published.
7. A. Blázquez, V. Mantič, F. Paris and L. N. McCartney, ‘BEM analysis of damage progress in 0/90 laminates’, *Engineering Analysis with Boundary Elements*, **33**, 762–769, 2009.